

APPROACHES TO SIMULTANEOUS INTERPRETATION STUDY

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Abstract: The main characteristics of a specific human activity are its motivational and target sides, subject, product and structure of activity. In this paper, the most essential concepts for the description of simultaneous interpretation are the concepts of purpose and structure of activity.

Keywords: translation, transformation, linguistic basis, activity based approach.

The word “translation” (meaning an interlanguage translation) is usually used in two meanings: as the end result of the translator’s work and as a process. In this monograph, the word “translation” will mean the translation process. If necessary, the term “translation text” will be used to name the product of translation activity (text is a sentence actually expressed, expressed or recorded, or a set of sentences of any length (Ахманова О.С., 2004: 470 and 365).

Translation, being a complex object, implies the possibility and legitimacy of studying it from various positions, within the framework of various scientific disciplines. With the currently most common linguistic approach, translation is understood as “interlanguage transformation or transformation of a text in one language into a text in another language” (Бархударов Л.С., 2021: 6; Комиссаров В.П., 1973; Рецкер Я.И., 1974; Швейцер А.Д., 1973; Федоров А.В., 1968; Catford J., 1965; Nida E., 1969). The progress of linguistic study of translation is indisputable.

Along with the linguistic approach, the psychological approach to the analysis of translation is of interest (Артемов В.А., 1969; Беляев Б.В., 1963; Зимняя И.А., 1975).

The psycholinguistic approach to translation is based on the principles of the theory of speech activity. The psychological basis is laid by the works of L.S. Vygotsky, A.N. Leontiev and A.R. Luria, the linguistic basis is laid by the works of I.A. Baudouin de Courtenay and L.V. Shcherba. Currently, the theory of speech activity is most actively developed by A.A. Leontiev, I.A. Zimnaya, etc. (see the collective monograph «Основы теории речевой деятельности», 1974).

The psycholinguistic approach to simultaneous interpretation means its activity representation, i.e. its interpretation as a certain type of activity (for example, the approach to professional translation as an activity in the book by Krupnov V.N., 1976).

In the general scheme of human activity, three spheres are usually distinguished: cognitive, socio-industrial and communicative-social (Зимняя И.А., 1974: 66). Simultaneous interpretation can be considered as an independent type (variety) of speech activity in the field of communicative and social activities.

The goal of the activity (we are talking about a goal that is subjectively realized) is understood as the final result, which the activity is aimed at achieving. It should be noted that, the overall goal of the activity is usually divided into its constituent intermediate goals, the consistent implementation of which leads to the final result.

The structure of an activity is formed by a sequence or other grouping of its constituent actions. Action is understood as a process aimed at achieving a subjectively realized intermediate goal. Actions, in turn, consist of operations. Unlike the goals of actions, the goals of operations are not subjectively realized – the operations are automated. Therefore, operations are correlated not with the goal, but with the conditions of execution.

The structure of the activity has great mobility due to the dynamism of its constituent actions and operations. For example, at the initial stage of mastering an activity, when the achievement of the final result is divided into many small steps with a subjective awareness of their goals, the structure of the activity consists of a correspondingly large number of actions. When, with progress along the path of mastering the activity, some intermediate steps begin to be carried out without difficulty and without awareness of their goals, there is an enlargement of the structural units of activity: some actions are automated, turn into operations and are included in larger actions. If the level of ownership of the activity remains constant, its structure can also be transformed. Thus, when conditions become more complicated and difficulties arise, the goals of some operations begin to be realized, the actions that include them are enlarged, turn into separate actions and the structure of the activity is fragmented. Therefore, any description of the structure of the activity should be understood conditionally, as correlated with a certain level of ownership of the activity and with specific conditions for its implementation. “The activity is based on a fixed system of reference points and is carried out under the influence of known constant factors that somehow guide this activity...” (Леонтьев А.А., 1974: 41). At the same time, “... activity cannot be characterized as something completely deterministic in all its concrete manifestations, it cannot be considered as a rigid system working according to a predetermined exact plan” (ibid.).

The activity-based approach to simultaneous interpretation involves such an analysis of the simultaneous interpreter’s activities, which leads to the identification of its structural units and the disclosure of the relations characterizing them. For example, the activity-based approach involves the search for answers to the questions: which units make up the activities of a simultaneous interpreter, how actions are combined into activities, through which operations actions are implemented in various conditions of activity.

With this approach, the problem of establishing the structure of activity comes first. The analysis of the characteristics of the structure of the simultaneous interpreter’s activity can be carried out in the following areas:

- analysis of the activity structure and the structure of its constituent actions;
- analysis of typical conditions for performing actions and their impact on the structure of activity;
- study of the features of operating with the material that makes up the object of activity.

In accordance with this problem, in separate chapters of the dissertation there are considered, the structure of the activity of a simultaneous interpreter, the essence of the simultaneity of perception of the source text and the generation of the text in the target language, the time constraints imposed on the activity of a simultaneous interpreter, and finally, the linguistic specifics of simultaneous interpretation.

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